

THE STAGES OF DEVELOPING GREEN ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. The development of a green economy in Uzbekistan represents a critical step towards sustainable growth and environmental conservation. This article examines the key stages of Uzbekistan's transition, including policy formulation, renewable energy implementation, green agriculture promotion, and sustainable urban development. By leveraging innovative technologies and international cooperation, Uzbekistan is positioning itself as a regional leader in green economy development.

Keywords: Green economy, Uzbekistan, sustainable development, renewable energy, green agriculture, environmental policy

Introduction. The transition to a green economy is a vital global movement addressing the dual challenges of economic development and environmental sustainability. Uzbekistan has taken significant steps to embrace this model, driven by both necessity and opportunity.

The foundation of Uzbekistan's green economy development was laid through the adoption of comprehensive policies and strategic plans. The most notable milestone was the approval of the National Strategy on Transition to a Green Economy for 2019–2030. This document outlined a roadmap for improving energy efficiency, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and promoting renewable energy [1]. For instance, the government set ambitious goals to ensure that renewable energy constitutes 25% of the country's energy mix by 2030. The focus on solar and wind energy, which are abundant in Uzbekistan, was a significant step forward. One practical example of this is the construction of the Navoi Solar Power Plant, which generates 100 megawatts (MW) of clean energy annually, contributing to a reduction of 160,000 tons of CO₂ emissions each year. Additionally, Uzbekistan joined international environmental agreements, such as the Paris Climate Agreement, which further strengthened its commitment to global sustainability goals.

The next critical phase was the implementation of renewable energy projects. With over 300 sunny days annually, Uzbekistan holds immense potential for solar energy development. Recognizing this, the government collaborated with international organizations like the World Bank and the Asian Development

Bank (ADB) to attract investments in green energy infrastructure. One landmark project is the Scaling Solar Initiative, which aims to create up to 1,000 MW of solar capacity. The Navoi and Samarkand regions were selected as pilot sites, and both regions are now home to modern solar farms that supply clean energy to the national grid [4, 69-74].

Furthermore, wind energy projects have gained momentum. For example, the Zarafshan Wind Farm, with a planned capacity of 500 MW, is expected to power 500,000 households while preventing 1.1 million tons of CO₂ emissions annually. These initiatives demonstrate how Uzbekistan is diversifying its energy portfolio to ensure long-term sustainability.

Agriculture, which contributes significantly to Uzbekistan's GDP, has also undergone a green transformation. Recognizing the environmental impact of conventional farming practices, the government introduced sustainable agriculture programs that prioritize water-saving technologies and eco-friendly fertilizers. Drip irrigation systems, which are widely used in the Ferghana Valley, serve as a prime example. These systems reduce water consumption by up to 40%, which is critical in a country where water resources are scarce. Additionally, organic farming practices have been encouraged through subsidies and training programs, helping farmers adopt methods that protect soil health and reduce chemical usage. Another noteworthy initiative is the introduction of climate-resilient crops, such as drought-resistant wheat varieties. These efforts aim to mitigate the adverse effects of climate change on agricultural productivity [2, 12-19].

Urban areas in Uzbekistan are also becoming more environmentally friendly. Projects such as the Green Cities Development Program focus on creating eco-friendly infrastructure, reducing air pollution, and promoting public transportation. For instance, in Tashkent, the metro system has been expanded to reduce reliance on private vehicles, thus lowering greenhouse gas emissions. Additionally, tree-planting campaigns have been launched in urban areas to improve air quality and provide shade, particularly during the scorching summer months. Solid waste management has also improved through recycling programs. The construction of waste-to-energy plants in cities like Namangan and Bukhara demonstrates the government's efforts to convert waste into a resource, reducing landfill dependency.

Conclusion. Uzbekistan's journey towards a green economy reflects a balance between ambition and pragmatism. Through strategic policies, renewable energy projects, green agriculture, and sustainable urban development, the

country has made remarkable strides. The green transition is not merely an environmental necessity; it is a pathway to long-term prosperity for Uzbekistan and its people.

References:

1. www.lex.uz/ Government of Uzbekistan. (2019). National Strategy on Transition to a Green Economy for 2019–2030.
2. Bo'rixadjayeva, M. S. (2023). O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTI VA IQTISODIYOTINI "YASHILLASHTIRISH" TAMOYILLARINI JORIY QILISH MASALALARI. World scientific research journal, 19(1), 12-19.
3. Feruz, B., & Islombek, U. (2024). O'ZBEKISTONNING YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHINI TA'MINLASH: MAVJUD HOLAT VA KELAJAK PROGNOZIKASI. Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования, 20(2), 158-161.
4. Xodjayeva, M. U. (2024). YANGI O'ZBEKISTONNI "YASHIL" IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH ISTIQBOLLARI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(4), 69-74.
5. Zairovich, V. E. (2024). YASHIL IQTISODIYOT ASOSIDA BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHNI TA'MINLASH XALQARO TAJRIBA. WORLD OF SCIENCE, 7(3), 155-158.